

EFFECTS OF TEACHER'S MOTIVATION ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AT PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN KARACHI PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

Research shows that the retention of entirely motivated teachers has had a powerful impact on students' performance. Public schools still need to maintain and sustain the motivation of teachers. Variables in research can help the school management retain teachers' lost motivation. The variables compensation, working condition, and working experience are not supported through research; one variable, professional development, is significant. This study aimed to determine factors based on motivation in public sectors in Karachi district South secondary schools. A total of the teachers of the public sectors in District South, Karachi were taken as population, and 140 respondents constitute the study sample by simple random sampling. The questionnaire was designed based on choices and used for data collection. The data was analyzed through SPSS in terms of frequency distribution and percentage. Finding suggested that all teachers were motivated and satisfied with the school's working conditions, which ultimately enhanced students' academic performance in class and at school.

KEYWORDS: *Compensation, Working Condition, Professional Development, Teacher Motivation, Academic performance*

INTRODUCTION

In developed countries, it is observed that education has played a vital role in nation-building and financial growth. For this purpose, they have built educational institutions in the shape of schools so that they may establish skills, knowledge and attitudes. For the betterment of the individual and organizations, clear goals are set so they can work precisely on them, and without wasting time and energy, they can achieve them. This strategy works very well for better student and teacher performance or employers and employees. Alarm and Farid (2011) favors this and consider them fundamental factors for excellent performance. This fact is also supported by Marques (2010), including motivation and satisfaction. Pakistani teachers have low motivation, the reason for the low salary and the absence of incentives, and they are also not considered an icon and respected in our society as they deserve. In addition, these classrooms need to be better equipped, and the risk of job satisfaction is shallow. Okumbe (1998) has clearly described the promotion and procedures with the environment that may motivate and de-motivate.

The Ministry of Education of Pakistan also acknowledges the above factors for the most negligible proper production in Pakistan, and they are ready to improve through proper channels. Further, motivation is mentioned in detail, intrinsic and extrinsic, performance and resources. According to (Okumbe, 1999), schools are nurturing points with two aims: performance goals and organizational maintenance goals. Schools are to be making strives to develop high performers in country-level examinations. Maintenance goals ensure survival. Extra-curricular activities, discipline and social images are the prime part of it. On the other hand, school's systems are providing quality education with proper inputs and outputs.

The quality of teaching and learning is the responsibility of schools; the quality of education in terms of teaching may enhance the work between teachers' work and Students' work to achieve goals. Most importantly, the teacher's motivation presents the teacher's energy.

According to Sogomo (1993) paying teachers extra money may bring a positive class revolution. The need for more teaching resources and learning resources may cause of producing effective leadership, which is created by a lack of teacher motivation. He further has brought it to our notice that teachers are unhappy, frustrated and uninspired as it is also observed in Pakistan teachers are at the peak of frustration and disappointment. There could be many reasons, including appreciation and less payment. The second reason is school environment is so suffocated that they

cannot freely cultivate creativity in students because of the status quo. The schools still need to be fully equipped. If they are, the equipment needs to be updated. Teachers feel unsafe, and they have to work in unhealthy conditions. In some cases, non-educational staff is dictating educational staff which is embarrassing for them. Another reason they are not provided training is that we have fewer opportunities to train teachers according to their subjects (Ali, Shah & Ahmad, 2023).

On the whole research problem addressed in this study, despite Pakistan's poor academic performance from 2018 – 2019, very few sincere efforts have been made to assess the Motivating Effect of Teachers on students' High school performance. This study was implemented in some regions on teacher motivation, and its impact on student performance shows that the results of a 7-motivated teacher are higher than a de-motivated teacher. Apart from motivation, some other factors have their own indication and contribution to the academic performance of learners within and without the schools and institutions. Finally, very highly motivated teachers have got much influence on the academic execution of learners within the institution and its surroundings.

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Okumbe (1998), "motivation is the process that starts with a physiological weakness or demand that ignites a behavior or a drive that is aimed towards a goal or an incentive. Marques (2010) asserts that energy is driven by the need to do better and that it can only be effective if the correct person is in control of the activity. How well employees perform their tasks depends on the efficiency and productivity of each organization. There are, however, certain other factors like employment analysis, employee recruitment, employee selection and employment placement. The motivations of employees and their willingness to work and do jobs are among these factors (Ngumi, 2003).

Motivation is a dimension that has been dealt with very carefully to understand the working environment of the individual worker (Wofford, 1971). It is noted that companies' production increases when employees are delighted. Improving any factor can be satisfactory and even eliminate any factor leading to dissatisfaction (Mutie, 1993). The focus of any organization's productivity is on improving employee satisfaction. If they are successful with the organization, they are happy or unhappy with the results. It is, therefore, directly proportional to any organization's work satisfaction and productivity. Motivation is a framework covering every reason, even harmful and cheerful, like money, promotion and recognition.

There are two intrinsic and extrinsic sources of motivation. Inside, people are motivated to do particular work because they know what they will get, and it does not depend on happiness or fortune. Foreign factors such as promotion or incentives rely on external motivation. To appreciate employees' effort or work in developing nations, management supplies these external variables; teachers' motivation has been extensively evaluated and researched. In contemporary, affluent nations, the issue of teachers' motivation is heavily discussed.

INTRINSIC AND EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION

(Mamoria & Gankar, 2005) The objective is to create conditions in which people are willing to work enthusiastically, take an initial step, and take interest and personal and collective satisfaction with pure responsibility, dedication, discipline, and pride in order to achieve the organization's goals. This study emphasizes on motivation because it has a substantial impact on teachers' work performance. In all regions of the globe, every educational system exhibits phenomenal expansion and enduring motivation. Alongside professional knowledge, skills, resources, and strategies, they may be the inevitable determinants of educational achievement and performance. Professional know-how and central skills are carried out when a person feels effective or careful in his / her behavior. Professional knowledge and competencies can be observed or considered when a single person is excellent during his or her educational success and performance challenges.

INTRINSIC MOTIVATION

The content theorist is very much focused on identifying needs that are given priority. Intrinsic rewards take the teachers beyond their benefit, such as salaries and their own identification in society, especially in the teaching profession. One who takes tasks or activities delightfully and satisfactorily means he/she is internally motivated. According to Stephen and Timothy (2008), teachers' attitudes and reactions can direct toward success and failure. Achievement, recognition, advancement and the possibility of growth can cause the reasons for intrinsic motivation by Herzberg (1968), and opportunities for personal and professional growth can matter in professional development.

According to Sogomo's (1993) observation, teachers in American elementary schools feel more important and recognized when their administrators and supervisors do so rather than their coworkers or peers. One trait of a great leader is that they publicly and immediately acknowledge and praise their team members for a job well done, which boosts morale and pride. A survey on the motivation of various level teachers in schools was taken as part of a study on "Listen and Learn": A policy report on Papua New Guinean teachers' attitude toward their profession, which was conducted in that country.

EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION

As described by Luthan (1998), Extrinsic rewards are tangible benefits which can be seen as tangible benefits, including employment pay, extra benefits or additional benefits, physical conditions, workload and working facilities. Extrinsic factors such as people meeting interpersonal relationships, policy, supervision, coworkers, coworkers, and subordinates influence workers' external motivation (Dornye, 2008).

The attractive setting in which the work is carried out or done can be a source of external motivation. Wahyuni (2020) studied the motivational patterns of teachers. Because of fewer facilities and a poor lifestyle, it is challenging to work in villages (rural areas) and more motivating than in the city (urban areas). Even in Pakistan, teachers are disadvantaged, so many findings lead to low motivation for teachers in rural regions.

In the form of wasting time in teaching, this scene or context has serious consequences. The motivation intrinsic and external to knowledge acquirement and dissemination of knowledge play an essential and practical role. A large amount or fewer resources, such as physical equipment and educational material, directly affect teachers' performance as the curriculum is effectively implemented. Finally, teachers must be highly motivated to provide complete services to their students through workload, remuneration, promotion and conducive education. We have got a vital difference between motivated behavior and motivational factors. It is impacted by reasons of motivation (Lens, & Decruyenaere, 1991).

Expectation, value and practical components are all factors (Peetsma, Hascher, Vander Veen & Roede, 2005). The students who are slow in performance, these teachers who have self-efficacy are found to be more involved with these students. Research shows that teachers with self-efficacy positively assist other teachers in their professional learning and enhance their Instruction quality (Geisel et al., 2009; Wheatley, 2002). The Value component defines and shows the intensity of teacher interest and the importance of achieving the goal and tasks. It also tells a teacher's belief in personal goals and how he thinks about his capacity to achieve them (Bandura, 1997).

Research regarding teacher commitment shows that if the teacher is committed to organizational goals and values and wholeheartedly accepts them, it can bring change significantly (Geijsel et al., 2009; Leithwood, Jantzi & Steinbach, 1999). Therefore, if an organization's goals and values are interconnected with teachers' personal beliefs, they may bring significant change (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

The 3rd factor of motivation is the affective component which defines teachers' feelings and emotions connected with the tasks. Many researchers have also emphasized considering or analyzing teachers' emotions through teacher promotion, learning environment and mass-reform processes. Teachers sometimes are uncertain because of the policy change in educational sectors, and they may be unable to work systematically (Sorrentino and Short, 1986). The further details through these researches are that teachers tend to work less infrequently by avoiding risk. They may need to maintain their attitude toward their job despite uncertain policies in educational sectors (Calef & Lortie, 1975; Rosenholtz, 1991).

METHODOLOGY

The data from the respondents were gathered and put together using a quantitative research design (Creswell, 2014). This study looked at the motivation of the teachers and how it affected the academic achievement of the students. All male and female secondary school teachers in District South, Sindh, Pakistan were the study's targeted population, and they were chosen by a straightforward random selection approach. A self-created survey questionnaire with 18 research items was used to gather the data. The research questionnaire was divided into two components. The first section asked about the demographics, gender, qualifications, and experience of the instructors. Face validity and reliability was ensured by the experts. The reliability analysis of instrument was satisfactory. The Cronch's Bach Alpha was 0.85, which shows that the instrument was reliable for the study. The second section asked about the teachers' thoughts on teacher motivation and how it affected students' academic achievement. Prior to being given to the respondents, the survey questionnaire was finalized and validated, and the respondents provided their consent. 200 survey forms were sent out to the participants, who were told to carefully read the provided statements and choose the appropriate response using a Likert scale with a range of 1 to 5, with 5 being a strong agreement. 140 completed survey forms out of 200 total were deemed suitable for data analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

The study's goal was to examine teachers' perceptions about motivation and its effect on students' academic achievement. The analysis contains information about the respondents' demographics, which were analyzed through SPSS version 22.

DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION OF THE PARTICIPANTS

In this study, one hundred forty teachers were selected that voluntarily took part in the research. There were a total of 70 females (50% of the total), and 70 males (50% of the total). The academic qualification showed that the majority of the participants have graduation degree 128(91%) rest of the participants were having the master's

qualification 12(09%). In the same manner experience distribution showed that the majority, of 44(31.4%) of the population, have between the 16-25 years' experience. As can be seen in the (table1).

Table 1

Demographic Information

		Frequency.	Percent.	Cumulative Percent.
Gender	Female	70	50	50
	Male	70	50	50
	Total	140	100.0	100
Qualification	Graduation	128	91	91
	Masters	12	09	09
	Total	140	100.0	100
Experience	2-5 yrs	28	20.0%	20
	6-10 yrs	32	22.8%	22.8
	11-15 yrs	36	25.8%	25.8
	16-25 yrs	44	31.4%	31.4
	Total	140	100%	100

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 2 Teaching gives me a chance to 'pay back' the good teachers I have had.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	52	37.2%
Agree	70	50.0%
Neutral	16	11.4%
Disagree	02	1.4%
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	150	100%

As shown in Table 2, secondary school teachers' replies to the statement "Teaching gives me a chance to "pay back" the good teachers I've had" 52 respondents had opinions that were overwhelmingly in agreement (37.2%), 70 agreed (or 50%), 16 had neutral thoughts (11.4%), and only 2 had disagreements (1.4%). According to the study's findings, the majority of survey respondents concurred that teaching affords me the chance to "pay back" the fantastic professors I've had.

Table 3 Teaching allows me to experience the love and respect of children.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	45	32.2%
Agree	88	62.8%
Neutral	06	4.3%
Disagree	01	0.7%
Strongly Disagree	--	--

Total	140	100%
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The findings of respondents who are secondary school teachers discussing how teaching enables them to feel the love and respect of youngsters are presented in Table 3. The opinions of 45 respondents were highly in agreement (32.2%), 88 were in agreement (62%), 06 were neutral (4.3%), and only one person objected (0.7%). According to the study's findings, the majority of participants agreed that teaching gave them the opportunity to witness children's love and respect.

Table 4 I would like to solve some of the problems in the educational system.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	47	33.7%
Agree	90	64.2%
Neutral	02	1.4%
Disagree	01	0.7%
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

The results of secondary school teachers who were asked if they would like to fix some issues with the educational system are shown in Table 4. A total of 90 respondents agreed, or 64%, with the opinion of 47 respondents, of whom 2 (1.4%) were indifferent and 1 (0.7%) disagreed. According to the study's findings, the majority of participants believed that I should try to fix some of the issues with the educational system.

Table 5 Teaching was the best job among those readily available to me.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	44	31.4%
Agree	87	62.2%
Neutral	07	5.0%
Disagree	01	0.7%
Strongly Disagree	01	0.7%
Total	140	100%

Table 5 displays the responses of secondary school teachers to the question, "Which of the available jobs was the best for me?" The opinions of 44 respondents were strongly agreeing (31.4%), 87 were agreeing (62.2%), 7 were neutral (5%), 1 was disagreeing (0.7%), and 1 was strongly disagreeing (0.7%). According to the study's findings, the vast majority of participants concurred that teaching was the best job available to me.

Table 6. I feel a personal 'calling' to teach.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	46	31.4%

Agree	89	63.5%
Neutral	04	5.0%
Disagree	01	0.7%
Strongly Disagree	--	0.7%
Total	140	100%

I sense a personal "calling" to teach, according to secondary school teachers, as seen in Table 6. Strong agreement was expressed by 46 respondents (31.4%), 87 respondents agreed (62.2%), 07 respondents (5%) were neutral, 01 respondents disagreed (0.7%), and 1 respondent severely disagreed (0.7). The majority of the participants in the survey agreed, according to the study's findings, that I have a personal "calling" to teach.

Table 7. I have a desire to impart knowledge to other people.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	60	42.8%
Agree	70	50.0%
Neutral	08	5.8%
Disagree	02	1.4%
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 7 lists the responses from secondary school teachers who were asked if they had a desire to teach others. The opinions of 60 respondents were highly in agreement (42.8%), 70 agreed (or 50%), 8 were neutral (5.8%), and 2 disagreed (1.4%). According to the study's findings, the majority of participants agreed that I am motivated to teach others.

Table 8 Teaching offers me a job with security.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	46	32.9%
Agree	92	65.7%
Neutral	01	0.7%
Disagree	01	0.7%
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Results from secondary school teachers who responded to the question "Teaching offers me a job with security" are shown in Table 8. There were 46 respondents who strongly agreed (32.9%), 92 who agreed (65.7%), 01 who were

neutral, and 01 who disagreed (0.7%). According to the study's findings, the majority of participants thought that teaching gives stable employment.

Table 9: People often regard me as a natural teacher.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	46	31.4%
Agree	89	63.5%
Neutral	04	5.0%
Disagree	01	0.7%
Strongly Disagree	--	0.7%
Total	140	100%

Table 9 displays the responses of secondary school teachers regarding People frequently see me as a natural teacher. There were 46 respondents who highly agreed (31.4%), 87 who agreed (62.2%), 07 (5%) who were neutral, 01 who disagreed (0.7%), and 01 who severely disagreed (0.7). According to the study's findings, the majority of participants agreed that people frequently see me as a natural instructor.

Table 10: The time schedule will be compatible with my home situation.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	43	30.7%
Agree	94	67.2%
Neutral	03	2.1%
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 10 displays the responses from secondary school teachers regarding the timetable that will work with my personal circumstances. 43 respondents (30.7%) expressed a strong consensus, 94 (67.2%) agreed, and 3 (2.1%) did not. According to the study's findings, the majority of participants believed that the time plan would work with my living circumstances.

Table 11: I feel comfortable working in this school.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	42	30.0%
Agree	75	53.5%
Neutral	13	9.2%
Disagree	06	4.2%

Strongly Disagree	04	2.8%
Total	140	100%

Table 11 lists the responses from secondary school teachers who were asked if they felt at ease working there. 75 respondents agreed, or 53.5%, with 42 respondents strongly agreeing (30%); the remaining 13 respondents (9.2%) were neutral; six respondents disagreed (4.2%); and four respondents strongly disagreed (2.8%). The majority of the participants in the study agreed, according to the study's findings, that I feel at ease working in this institution.

Table 12: I am facilitated to overcome limitations in my experience.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	43	30.8%
Agree	90	64.2%
Neutral	07	5.0%
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 12 shows the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding I am facilitated to overcome limitations in my experience. 43 respondent's opinion were strongly agreeing (30.8%), agreed were 90 which is (64.2%) and from which 07 (5%) were neutral. According to study findings, the majority of participants agreed that I am helped to overcome experience-related constraints.

Table 13: Professional development brings positive change in professional attitude.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	64	45.7%
Agree	76	54.3%
Neutral	--	--
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 13 shows the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding Professional development bringing positive change in professional attitude. Sixty-four respondents strongly agreed (45.7%), and 76 agreed (54.3%). The study results stated that most participants agreed that Professional development brings positive change in professional attitude.

Table 14: Professional development directly improve the students learning process

Level	Frequency	Percentage
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Strongly Agree	40	28.6%
Agree	80	57.2%
Neutral	15	10.7%
Disagree	05	3.5%
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 14 revealed the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding Professional development directly improving the student's learning process. Forty respondents' opinions strongly agreed (28.6%), agreed, 80 agreed (57.2%), of which 15 (10.7%) were neutral, and 05 disagreed (3.5%). The study's results stated that Professional development improves the student's learning process.

Table 15: Professional development is helpful in achieving student's achievement

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	42	30%
Agree	91	65%
Neutral	07	5.0%
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

The responses from secondary school teachers regarding the value of professional development in raising student achievement are shown in Table 15. The opinions of 42 respondents were extremely agreed (30%), 91 were agreed (65%), and 7 (5%) were neutral. The majority of participants, according to the study's findings, felt that professional development aids in student accomplishment.

Table 16 Professional development enhances student's cognitive skills.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	62	44.2%
Agree	78	55.8%
Neutral	--	--
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 16 shows the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding Professional development enhancing students’ cognitive skills. Sixty-two respondent’s opinion was strongly agreed (44.2%), and agreed were 76 agreed (55.8%). The study results stated that most participants agreed that Professional development enhances students’ cognitive skills.

Table 17: Professional development is helpful in developing critical thinking among students

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	40	28.5%
Agree	90	64.3%
Neutral	10	7.2%
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 17 describes the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding Professional development as helpful in developing critical thinking among students. Forty respondents' opinions were strongly agreed (28.5%), agreed were 90 agreed (64.3%) and from which 10 (7.2%) were neutral. The study results stated that most participants agreed that Professional development helps develop critical thinking among students.

Table 18: It raises curiosity among students

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	66	47.2%
Agree	74	52.8%
Neutral	--	--
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 18 shows the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding it raises curiosity among students. 66 respondent’s opinion was strongly agreeing (47.2%) and agreed were 74 which are (52.8%). According to the study's findings, the majority of participants agreed that it inspires pupils' curiosity.

Table 19: It is helpful in developing self confidence among students.

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	44	31.4%
Agree	92	65.8%
Neutral	04	2.8%

Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 19 shows the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding it helping develop self-confidence among students. Forty-four respondent’s opinions were strongly agreed (31.4%), agreed were 92 which is (65.8%) and from which 04 (2.8%) were neutral. The study results stated that most participants agreed that It helps develop self-confidence among students.

Table 20: It helps in developing reading and writing skills among students

Level	Frequency.	Percentage.
Strongly Agree	58	41.4%
Agree	82	58.6%
Neutral	--	--
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 20 lists the responses from secondary school teachers indicating how it aids in students' acquisition of reading and writing skills. Strong agreement was expressed by 58 respondents (41.4%), and agreement was expressed by 82 respondents (58.6%). According to the study's findings, the majority of participants agreed that it aids in kids' acquisition of reading and writing abilities.

Table 21 It promotes mutual cooperation among students

Level	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly Agree	53	37.8%
Agree	83	59.4%
Neutral	04	2.8%
Disagree	--	--
Strongly Disagree	--	--
Total	140	100%

Table 21 shows the results of respondents of secondary school teachers regarding it promotes mutual cooperation among students. 53 respondent’s opinion was strongly agreeing (37.8%), agreed were 83 which are (59.4%) and 04 were neutral (2.8%). According to the study's findings, the majority of participants agreed that it encourages pupils to work together.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

According to the findings of recent studies, a shift in how teachers feel about their own professional growth may be one factor that contributes to students' overall improvement in their academic achievement. The findings of this study are predicated on ideas that were borrowed from a variety of educational theorists (Raza & Ahmed, 2017; Ali, Ahmad, & Sewani, 2022). These ideas include the notion that motivation can be either intrinsic or extrinsic, and these ideas were put into practice by means of goal-setting, reinforcement, equity, and rewards. A conceptual structure for the first hypothesis is that continuing education for instructors is the most important factor in reviving classroom enthusiasm. This is because it keeps educators current with the most recent strategies for keeping students interested. The second hypothesis states that monetary rewards have the potential to fully motivate teachers to improve their pupils' academic achievement. The third hypothesis states that having more job experience improves one's ability to teach and deal with academic pupils. A completely stimulating environment may be brought into classrooms by maintaining ideal working conditions, and teachers bring their own vibrations into the classroom as a result of their years of experience, which in turn affects how kids learn.

We also took into consideration and thought about the factors that influence motivation, such as pay and benefits, working conditions, and opportunities for professional growth and further work experience. Finally, the results of this investigation matched up well with the existing body of knowledge, which validates our efforts.

Therefore, continued professional development for educators may bring about a significant shift in the academic performance of their students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The result of the current research indicated that teacher's motivation may be achieved by giving them training for their development and this may cause a huge positive change in students' academic performance.

By training teachers, we may establish skills, knowledge and attitudes. This can help to bring the teachers growth for the long term and sustain their motivation.

The professional development courses will permit teachers to become knowledgeable to provide alterations and changes in course work as well.

Learners tend to learn through a specific kind of energy which is out source of or sometimes in source of energy.

The upcoming researchers are recommended to discover more and more about some elements that may be useful for teachers' opinions and attitude.

Some more study is required to find out as many facts and aspects as possible.

Consequently, the upcoming facts and opinions could be beneficial for the teachers' motivation and would have direct or indirect impact on students' academic performance.

Diversified research may bring some new elements which may be effective for teacher's motivation somehow.

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